

HOMOEOPATHIC MANAGEMENT OF VIRAL CONJUNCTIVITIS : A CASE REPORT

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Abstract— Conjunctivitis is one of the most common causes of red-eye and affects patients of all ages and socioeconomic class. Viral conjunctivitis is responsible for the majority of infectious conjunctivitis, accounting for up to 75% of cases[1] A 24-year-old male patient treated successfully using Euphrasia 30 C on the basis of case analysis and individualization. This case highlighting the efficacy of Homeopathic remedies in viral conjunctivitis

Index Terms— Conjunctivitis, HOMOEOPATHIC

I. Introduction

Conjunctivitis, also known as "pink eye", is inflammation of the conjunctiva. The three most common causes of conjunctivitis are viral, allergic, and bacterial, and the majority of cases are caused by adenovirus. Conjunctivitis causes the eye to appear erythematous secondary to the dilation of blood vessels and is usually accompanied by increased tearing and/or mucoid discharge. This activity describes the risk factors, evaluation, and management of viral conjunctivitis and highlights the role of the interprofessional team in enhancing care delivery to affected patients.[2]

While conventional treatment approaches, such as antivirals and corticosteroids, are commonly used to manage viral conjunctivitis , they often have associated side effects and may not always provide complete relief. Homoeopathy, a holistic system of medicine, offers a safe and effective alternative approach to treating viral conjunctivitis . By addressing the underlying the root cause of the condition, constitutional factors and stimulating the body's natural healing abilities, Homoeopathy can provide long-lasting relief and prevent recurrence. [3]

Homoeopathy, a system of medicine based on the principle of "like cures like," has been used for centuries to treat a wide range of acute and chronic conditions, including viral conjunctivitis [4] By carefully selecting remedies based on the individual's unique symptom picture, Homoeopathy aims to stimulate the body's natural healing response and restore health[5].

This case report aims to illustrate the efficacy of Homoeopathic treatment in a patient presenting with viral conjunctivitis . By analyzing the patient's symptoms and selecting the most appropriate Homoeopathic remedy, a significant improvement in the patient's condition was achieved.

II. Methodology

Study Design-Descriptive case report

Thorough case was taken & case analysis showed -

A 34 year male Patient came to the OPD with complaint of redness of eyes or pink eye with irritation and burning in eyes . The patient developed redness and burning in eyes after exposing infected individual in his work place . Symptoms worsened during morning as he wake up and starts symptoms . The patient also experienced sticky discharges from both eyes and stiching type of pains in both eyes, and ptosis Mild fatigue and a low-grade fever (99.5°F) were noted.

Complaints aggravated by: Sunlight , warmth , Evening ameliorated by : open air , winking H/o of recurrent watery discharges from both the eyes which is acrid in nature * EYES B/L :Sticky discharges , whitish yellowish colour , epiphora Fear of light while opening the eyes * Temperature: 99.5°F. * Pulse: 84 bpm, regular.

III. Homeopathic Case Analysis

TOTALITY OF SYMPTOM [6,7] *Fear of light while opening the eyes *Yellowish whitish discharges *Profuse hot or acrid tears *Sensitive of cold and cold weather

IV. Reportization

1. Eyes – Photophobia
2. Eyes – discharges of mucus or pus – yellow
3. Eyes – Tears acrid
4. Eyes – Discharge of mucus or pus – sticky mucus on cornea
5. Generalities -cold agg

The screenshot shows a software interface for homeopathic repertorisation. At the top, it says 'Repertorisation' and 'Of Speed Case'. Below that, there are fields for 'Reg. No.' and 'Visit Date: 03/02/2026'. The main area is a grid with 'Remedy Name' on the left and various remedies (Euphr, Ars, Calc, Lyc, Sulph, Merc, Caust, Pu) as columns. The rows list symptoms: '[C] [Eye]Photophobia', '[C] [Eye]Discharges of mucus or pus:Yellow', '[C] [Eye]Tears:Acrid', '[C] [Eye]Discharges of mucus or pus:Sticky mucus on cornea', and '[C] [Generalities]Cold:Agg'. The 'Totality' row shows counts for each remedy: Euphr (13), Ars (10), Calc (10), Lyc (10), Sulph (10), Merc (9), Caust (8). The 'Symptoms' section at the bottom shows 5 symptoms entered.

Remedy Name	Euphr	Ars	Calc	Lyc	Sulph	Merc	Caust	Pu
Totality	13	10	10	10	10	9	8	
Symptom Covered	5	4	4	4	4	4	4	
[C] [Eye]Photophobia	3	3	3	3	3	3	2	
[C] [Eye]Discharges of mucus or pus:Yellow	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	
[C] [Eye]Tears:Acrid	3	3	2	2	3	2	2	
[C] [Eye]Discharges of mucus or pus:Sticky mucus on cornea	3							
[C] [Generalities]Cold:Agg	2	3	3	3	2	2	3	

V. Differential Remedy [8]

1. Euphrasia
2. Arsenic album
3. Calc carb
4. Lycopodium
5. Sulphur

VI. Final Remedy Selection

Based on repertorization and totality of symptoms, EUPHRASIA 30 C was prescribed Euphrasia 30C, 3 doses at 6 – hour interval, And may need to be adjusted based on patient's improvement.

VII. Follow up

- * Day 1: Euphrasia 30C, 3 doses at 6-hour intervals. Hot fomentation applied to advice
- * Day 2: Eye discharges significantly reduced. The patient reported reduced eye discharges and its acridity of tears
- * Day 4: Symptoms resolved completely. The patient resumed his duty without difficulty

Discussion

This case study showed the Homoeopathic management was effective in case of viral conjunctivitis and Euphrasia was selected as most appropriate remedy. The key factors that led to this choice include :-

Euphrasia - eyes are watery , acrid lachrymation which is aggravated in cold ++, fear of light , discharges are mucus , pus with stickiness is marked , pain in eyes.

Differential Diagnosis and Other Remedies Considered:

While Euphrasia was the primary remedy chosen, it is essential to consider other potential remedies and their differentiating features

1. Arsenic album – Keys -sunken and protruding eyes spasms of eyelids with edematous condition of eyelids
2. Calc carb – Keys - Pupils are dilated corneal ulcer is marked , intense lachrymation which is not acrid
3. Lycopodium – Keys - Hemiopia , day blindness, sparks before the eyes - in the dark , specially suited for cataract
4. Sulphur –Keys - bursting pain in eyeballs , halo around the light , eye inflammation by foreign bodies and specially for keratitis

Conclusion

This case study showed the Homoeopathic management was effective in case of Viral conjunctivitis with EUPHRASIA & further clinical evaluation for the many cases.

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